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CLIMATE RESILIENT AND ENVIRONMENTALLY
SUSTAINABLE TRANSPORT INFRASTRUCTURE,
WITH A FOCUS ON INLAND WATERWAYS

D3.4 Corridor visibility and common open data platform

**CRISTAL - Climate resilient and environmentally sustainable transport
infrastructure, with a focus on inland waterways**

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List of abbreviations

Abbreviation/Term	Description
AJAX	Asynchronous JavaScript And XML
API	Application Programming Interface
ARIA	Accessible Rich Internet Applications
CERTH	Centre for Research & Technology Hellas
CSS	Cascading Style Sheets
ETA	Estimated Time of Arrival
EU	European Union
HTML	HyperText Markup Language
HTTPS	HyperText Transfer Protocol Secure
IWT	Inland Waterway Transport
IWW	Inland Water Ways
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
ORM	Object Relational Mapping
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
LTS	Long-Term Support
POUR	Perceivable, Operable, Understandable, and Robust
REST	Representational State Transfer
SCMS	Synchro-modal Corridor Management System
SSL	Secure Sockets Layer
TLS	Transport Layer Security
UI	User Interface
UX	User Experience
WCAG	Web Content Accessibility Guidelines
WP	Work Package

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1. Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the development and implementation of the Corridor Visibility and Common Open Data Platform in the context of Task 3.4, a key digital component of the CRISTAL project's ambition to enhance synchro-modal and multimodal IWT across Europe. This platform is instrumental in improving corridor-level visibility, supporting data-driven decision-making, and enabling regional policy formulation, thus contributing directly to CRISTAL's overarching goals of modal shift, climate resilience, and transport efficiency.

This deliverable builds upon the architectural foundations laid in D3.1, the technologies and the implemented software infrastructure of the Synchro-modal Corridor Management System (SCMS) in D3.3 and leverages the Logistics Observatory previously adapted in the FENIX project for the Orient/East-Med TEN-T corridor. The platform has been customized for CRISTAL's designated corridors in the Italian, French, and Polish river pilots, integrating historical, static and real-time data to provide a comprehensive view of corridor operations. Key functionalities include infrastructure index, dashboards, operational and infrastructure metrics, all accessible through a user-friendly interface.

The report outlines the features and development of the platform, starting with information about the implemented functionalities, followed by the integration of the observatory functionalities and available data sources provision services. The platform's architecture and data analysis procedures are detailed, along with the technologies employed. A dedicated tutorial section introduces user personas, use cases, and accessibility considerations. The deliverable also identifies challenges encountered during data collection, digitalization, Key Performance Indicators (KPI) development and software development.

The implemented platform will offer valuable insights that will inform future iterations of the SCMS platform in D3.5, where the tools developed in the tasks 3.3 and 3.4 are integrated in the SCMS platform. The observatory can be accessed through the SCMS platform in following URL: <https://scms.imet.gr/>

In summary, D3.4 marks an important milestone in CRISTAL's digital innovation pathway, delivering a scalable, interoperable, and user-centric platform that enhances visibility and coordination along European inland waterway corridors.

1.1. Introduction

The main objective of this deliverable is to introduce the Corridor Visibility and Common Open Data Platform, a regional repository of multimodal transport data designed to support both operational and policy-level decision-making.

The platform follows the Logistics Observatory rationale of services that was previously adapted in the FENIX project for the Orient/East-Med TEN-T corridor. It is customized for CRISTAL's designated Italian, French and Polish corridors by offering services relevant to core infrastructure of each pilot corridor, dashboards and charts with overall metrics, KPIs and statistics, and also interactive maps for geo-localizing and visualizing the corridors' core infrastructure. It integrates a wide range of static and real-time data sources into a unified digital environment. This enables stakeholders to monitor corridor performance, assess infrastructure readiness and respond proactively to emerging challenges.

The Corridor Visibility and Common Open Data Platform developed in Task 3.4 has been designed to be fully compatible with the software infrastructure of the SCMS. As such, it may not be described as a standalone system, but it is intended to be offered as a core service within the SCMS environment. This architectural alignment ensures complete interoperability with other SCMS tools and services. The observatory can be accessed through the SCMS platform in following URL: <https://scms.imet.gr/>

Overall, the corridor visibility platform developed in this deliverable marks a significant step toward the digital transformation of IWW corridors, laying the groundwork for enhanced visibility, interoperability, and decision support across Europe’s multimodal transport networks. Beyond the project duration, the examined corridor use cases will be further refined in collaboration with pilot partners, guiding the implementation and integration of the platform within the broader SCMS ecosystem.

1.2. Mapping CRISTAL outputs

Table 1 Alignment of D3.4 contents to the corresponding GA deliverable & task(s) descriptions

CRISTAL GA Component Title	CRISTAL GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE			
<i>D3.4 Corridor visibility and common open data platform</i>	<i>Development of a Corridor visibility and common open data platform for enhancing visibility along the corridors and support decision making</i>	<i>2,3, 4 and 5</i>	<i>In these chapters, the architecture of the observatory is described, along with the included metrics, accessibility aspects, and the risks and challenges that emerged during development.</i>
TASKS			
<i>Task 3.4 Corridor visibility and common open data platform</i>	<i>A regional repository of information and data regarding synchro-modality/multi-modality and inland waterway transport is established to enhance visibility along the designated transport corridor, and support decision and policy-making at regional level.</i>	<i>2</i>	<i>In Chapter 2, the infrastructure index is presented, along with the operational and infrastructure metrics included in the observatory to provide visibility and to support decision-making and policy-making at the regional level.</i>

1.3. Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

This deliverable is structured into six chapters, each contributing to the documentation of the development and deployment of the Corridor Visibility and Common Open Data Platform.

- Chapter 1 includes the executive summary, introduction, and a description of the report's structure and alignment with the Grant Agreement.
- Chapter 2 presents the Corridor Observatory features, detailing the Infrastructure Index section and the definition of operational and infrastructure metrics, along with the KPIs that support corridor-level monitoring and operational assessment.
- Chapter 3 outlines the software architecture and data analysis procedures, explaining how the KPIs are calculated, including the technologies used and the system's modular design.
- Chapter 4 provides a usage tutorial for the SCMS Corridor Observatory, introducing user personas, use cases, and accessibility considerations in the developed user interface components.
- Chapter 5 discusses the challenges encountered during data gathering, KPI creation, and software development, along with the risk mitigation strategies applied.
- Finally, the sixth chapter concludes the report by summarizing the main outcomes of Task 3.4 and describing the next steps for platform enhancement and validation.

2. Corridor observatory

The Corridor Observatory and Common Open Data Platform is a comprehensive monitoring and analytics platform developed to offer an integrated view on the performance and infrastructure status of inland waterways. It combines infrastructure data, operational records, and sensor-based measurements into a single digital environment where users can explore the dynamics of corridor management. Its main goals are to promote long-term strategic IWW planning, enable data-driven decision-making, and increase transparency in waterway transport systems.

The Observatory is a monitoring tool and decision-support system that makes it easier to assess KPIs across several corridor management parameters. It creates a consistent framework for performance evaluation by connecting operational efficiency and reliability measures with infrastructure status. It is integrated inside the SCMS platform as a separate page and feature named “Corridor Observatory”. The Observatory provides open public access to all information and data, which are available for consultation by all SCMS users.

The Corridor Observatory's interactive map is a key component. Users may locate infrastructure assets like locks, bridges, river ports, intermodal terminals and navigable corridors, and identify rivers using the map. Through the integration of analytical dashboards and geographic visualization, the platform allows users to monitor and evaluate performance data related to the physical geography of transportation corridors. The Observatory's function as a useful management tool is enhanced by this spatial component, which connects intangible indications with actual locations.

The Corridor Observatory is organized around three core sections: Infrastructure Index, Operational Metrics, and Infrastructure Metrics. These modules work in combination to deliver complementary insights: Infrastructure Metrics enable a thorough analysis of river infrastructure, characteristics, and statistics, Operational Metrics highlight functional and operational efficiency, and the Infrastructure Metrics offers a complete view of how each river's infrastructure is and has been operating (Figure 1).

Corridor Observatory
This page provides an in-depth analysis of legend performance indicators (KPIs) and essential metrics pertaining to waterways, operational efficiency, and lock management.

Navigation: HOME | EARLY DETECTION & INFO | DISRUPTION IMPACT ESTIMATION | ACTION TOOLBOX SERVICES | **CORRIDOR OBSERVATORY** | QUICK TUTORIAL | LOG IN

Select River: PO | SEINE | MOSELLE | VISTULA | ODER | Infrastructure Index | Operational Metrics | Infrastructure Metrics

River Infrastructure & Characteristics					
Name	PO	Source Name	Monte Viso	Mouth Name	Adriatic Sea
Length	652 km	Basin Area	74000 km ²	Average Discharge	1540 m ³ /sec
Locks	18	Bridges	100		

Figure 1 The Corridor Observatory page (river Po)

2.1. Infrastructure index

The Infrastructure Index tab of the Corridor Observatory offers a structured overview of the physical and hydrological attributes of the inland waterways studied in the CRISTAL project. This page serves as a dashboard that combines important river infrastructure and characteristics data. This guarantees that users such as barge operators, academics, as well as various stakeholders and policymakers, can easily find important river information.

The section titled "River Infrastructure & Characteristics" serves as the foundational dataset for corridor evaluation. Each river entry is presented through modular cards designed to enhance readability and highlight key indicators. The dataset includes the following features:

- **Name:** The official name of the river.
- **Source and Mouth locations:** Defines the natural boundaries of the waterway.
- **Length (km):** A baseline measure of navigability.
- **Basin area (km²):** Represents the hydrological scope of the river system.
- **Average discharge (m³/s):** It reflects water volume and flow intensity.
- **Locks and Bridges:** Name and location of locks and bridges, imported manually from sectional data.
- **Ports and intermodal terminals:** Name and location of main seaports, river ports and intermodal terminals in the wider corridor area, imported manually from sectional data.

Together, this data establishes the infrastructure baseline that underpins subsequent performance assessments. Locks and bridges are particularly critical, as they directly influence operational efficiency and continuity as well as navigation reliability.

Accessibility is a core principle of the platform's design. A responsive grid layout ensures great usability across all devices, desktop, tablet, and mobile. Data is presented through color-coded cards, clear labels, and prominent numeric highlights, creating a visually consistent interface that enhances clarity and maintains a clean, professional appearance (Figure 2).

Figure 2 The River Infrastructure & Characteristics dashboard

2.2. Operational metrics

The Operational Metrics page of the Corridor Observatory presents a central analytical module, designed to assess the functional performance of inland waterway corridors. Its main purpose is to translate raw operational data into structured insights that carry's evidence-based decision-making, performance monitoring, and long-term strategic planning (Figure 3).

The Operational Metrics page functions as the core analytical engine of the Corridor Observatory, designed to monitor and evaluate the real-time performance of inland waterway corridors. It consolidates raw operational data into actionable insights, enabling users to:

- Track corridor efficiency through KPIs such as traffic volume, availability and reliability
- Identify bottlenecks and disruptions impacting multimodal connectivity and navigation reliability
- Support evidence-based decisions for operational adjustments and resource allocation
- Inform long-term strategic planning by analysing trends for metrics like cost efficiency and CO₂ emission savings

This module transforms complex datasets into structured dashboards and visual indicators, making sure that the operational visibility is translated into actionable insights (Figure 3).

Figure 3 The Operational Metrics page

The Operational Metrics interface is split into two main information panels:

1. **The Operational Metrics panel**
2. **The secondary Alerts Metrics panel**

The Operational Metrics panel provides a concise overview of operational key performance indicators and is positioned on the left-hand side of the interface. It displays critical variables such as traffic volumes, safety performance, availability, reliability, cost efficiency, and environmental impact, offering stakeholders an immediate snapshot of corridor functionality. The panel uses a scrollable, card-based layout combined with a consistent color palette to ensure legibility and maintain a clean visual identity across all screen sizes. This responsive design guarantees usability on desktop, tablet, and mobile devices. On the right-hand side, the Operational Metrics Over Time sub-section introduces an interactive chart that visualizes trends and patterns for selected metrics. Users can choose specific indicators such as traffic volume, CO₂ emission savings, or safety performance from a dropdown menu and adjust the observation window using radio-button filters (6 months, 1 year, or 2 years). The resulting dynamic charts enable users to track changes, monitor progress and compare operational outcomes across different timeframes.

Figure 4 The Operational Metrics panel

The Alerts Metrics sub-panel provides an interactive view of corridor disruptions within a user-defined timeframe. By selecting a start and end date through datetime pickers and clicking the “Search” button, users can retrieve the total number of alerts for the chosen period along with a detailed breakdown by alert type (Figure 5). This breakdown is presented in a table with three columns: Alert Type, Alerts Count, and Average Duration (Days), offering a clear operational snapshot. To complement the tabular data, the general Corridor Observatory map page element at the bottom of the page is enhanced with a geospatial heatmap that visualizes alert density across the corridor using a color scale that ranges from Low to High density (Figure 6). The map includes layer toggles for infrastructure elements such as locks, bridges, ports, and intermodal terminals, as well as a dedicated toggle for the alerts heatmap. Zooming out emphasizes overall density patterns, while zooming in reveals individual alert points represented as blue circles with white borders, each clickable to display the corresponding alert type (Figure 7). This interactive design enables users to quickly identify hotspots, correlate alerts with infrastructure and prioritize interventions for improved corridor resilience.

Figure 5 The Alerts Metrics panel

Figure 6 Alerts heatmap inside the Corridor Observatory

Figure 7 Alerts heatmap individual map points inside the Corridor Observatory

2.3. Infrastructure metrics

The Infrastructure Metrics page of the Corridor Observatory offers an asset-level view of corridor performance, with a particular focus on lock availability and functionality. Locks are critical components of inland waterway systems, enabling vessels to navigate elevation changes and ensuring uninterrupted transport operations. Their operational status directly influences corridor reliability and efficiency.

At the top of the interface, the system displays the total number of locks along the selected river, establishing the scope of analysis. Users can then refine their evaluation by selecting a custom timeframe using the From and To date fields. This feature supports multiple use cases, including long-term performance reviews, seasonal trend analysis, and short-term operational monitoring. Search results are presented in a dedicated section, complemented by two additional panels highlighting the least available and most available locks within the chosen timeframe (Figure 8). This structured approach enables users to quickly identify critical infrastructure constraints, assess operational continuity and prioritize maintenance or intervention strategies.

Figure 8 The Infrastructure Metrics tab page

The Infrastructure Metrics page also includes a lock identification feature that complements the timeframe selection. Users can quickly locate specific locks by entering a partial or full lock name in the search field, bringing the corresponding lock or even multiple locks to the top of the results for detailed analysis (Figure 9). This functionality is particularly valuable for maintenance planning, incident monitoring and targeted performance reviews, where specific assets require focused attention.

Figure 9 Filtering the locks by lock name

In addition to highlighting the selected locks in the results panel, the system displays them on the map while hiding non-matched locks, providing a clear view for spatial analysis (Figure 10).

Figure 10 Display of filtered locks inside the map

The locks returned by the search whether filtered or not, are displayed as individual cards, each featuring a “Show Details” button. When clicked, this button opens a modal overlay containing two interactive charts. The first is a vertical bar chart that illustrates lock availability over time, allowing users to select intervals of 6 months, 1 year, 2 years, or 3 years for trend analysis (Figure 11). The second chart is a pie chart that visualizes the loss of availability within the selected timeframe, breaking down the distribution of reasons for these outages. This dual-chart approach provides both a temporal and categorical perspective, helping users to quickly identify patterns and understand root causes.

Figure 11 Individual Lock availability insights

The map at the bottom of the Infrastructure Metrics page allows users to engage directly with lock elements. When a lock is clicked, a popup displays its current operational status, either open or closed, providing immediate insight into navigation availability (Figure 12).

Figure 12 Lock elements inside the map

From a functional perspective, the Infrastructure Metrics page of the Corridor Observatory operates as a diagnostic tool for asset-level performance analysis. While the Infrastructure Index provides an overview of the corridor and the Operational Metrics focus on utilization outcomes and possibilities, this module delivers detailed insights into individual infrastructure -namely locks- components.

- Find locks that are significantly causing delays to discover problems.
- Prioritize maintenance on underperforming assets to plan focused interventions.
- Monitor resilience and reliability at the most detailed level of the infrastructure network.

3. Software architecture and data analysis

This chapter presents the core architectural elements and data analysis capabilities underpinning the Corridor Visibility and Common Open Data Platform. Building upon the foundational design introduced in D3.1 and the technologies used for developing the SCMS platform as outlined in D3.3, it details the state of the software architecture and its alignment with the platform's functional and performance requirements. In addition, the chapter highlights the integration of data analysis components such as metrics, charts, and analytics that provide insights through KPIs, usage metrics and statistical summaries.

3.1. Technologies

As discussed in D3.3, the SCMS platform is a public service that emphasizes application availability, high performance, and open data access without the need of user authentication. The platform has an innovative, modular design with separate frontend, backend and infrastructure components.

The backend architecture is built on Laravel 10, the most popular PHP framework known for its integrated development tools and flexible syntax. Data access is managed through Eloquent Object Relational Mapping (ORM), which provides an object-oriented interface for the application's MySQL database, while phpMyAdmin ensures easy administrative access for developers.

To enable real-time functionality, the system leverages Laravel Events and Laravel Echo, combined with a Pusher-compatible Soketi WebSocket server for efficient server-sent event delivery to clients. Redis serves as queue backend used for asynchronous tasks such as email notifications, jobs queuing and event broadcasting and also functions as a caching layer to optimize performance and reduce database load. Application logging is handled through Laravel's Monolog-based multi-channel system for configurable and reliable log management.

The frontend/user interface (UI) part of the SCMS platform is styled using Tailwind CSS enabling fast, utility-first design for a responsive and consistent user interface. Digital mapping capabilities are enabled by combining Mapbox GL JS for high-performance vector maps with the Google Maps JavaScript API for geocoding and location-based services. Interactive behaviors are managed through JavaScript and jQuery, while real-time updates are delivered by subscribing to Laravel Echo channels, a JavaScript library that works seamlessly with Laravel Events.

During development, Node.js and Vite handle asset bundling and hot reloading, producing optimized builds for production. Continuous Integration and Deployment (CI/CD) is automated through GitLab CI, which also serves as the version control system, making sure that new SCMS software version releases are quick, efficient and repeatable.

The platform is fully containerized using Docker, isolating services such as Redis, MySQL, Nginx, Queue workers and Laravel/PHP for scalability and reliability. Production runs on Ubuntu 24.04 Long-Term Support (LTS) with Nginx acting as a reverse proxy to manage HTTPS traffic and static files, while local development leverages Laravel Sail for great developer experience. Certbot is integrated within the Docker environment to issue and automatically renew TLS/SSL certificates. Containerization supports horizontal scaling and robust component isolation.

Code quality is maintained through automated testing. PHPUnit validates backend components including controllers, models, and services via unit and integration tests. For frontend verification, Laravel Dusk performs end-to-end browser testing, simulating user interactions such as map rendering, form submissions, and real-time updates. Tests are automatically run with Gitlab CI pipelines on each Gitlab feature branch merge into the main development branch, as well as the second stage of the production release CI pipeline, where the first stage is a security check of the installed libraries inside the platform's backend and frontend parts.

3.2. Architecture overview

Although the Corridor Observatory feature is a component of the SCMS architecture's Application Layer, it depends on every underlying layer for data management, processing, and collecting. This architecture has been applied in practice, where the individual SCMS platform folders and files map to specific architecture elements.

Figure 13 Corridor Management System Architecture

The Corridor Observatory conforms to the established architecture with the following file and folder structure:

1. Application Layer:

- `ObservatoryController.php` handles the high-level operations of the Corridor Observatory.
- Uses middleware services to retrieve metrics and analytics insights.
- Data are ready and passed down to the Blade view templates for rendering in the UI.

2. Middleware Layer:

- It interacts with Eloquent ORM Models that handle database operations.
- Processes raw data from sensors, external systems and the digital twin by applying the appropriate business logic.

- Prepares KPI evaluation, data aggregation and alert generation for the Application layer.
- Services exist in directory `app/Services/` and called inside the `ObservatoryController.php`.

3. Data Sources & Connectivity Layer:

- Integrates external systems (e.g., EuRIS) and the Digital Twin.
- Provides the Observatory with both real-time and forecast datasets.

4. Configuration & Data Management Layer:

- MySQL stores historical and near-real-time data.
- Manual data insertion in the database are added via database migrations (`database/migrations/`) and seeder files.
- Database tables are mapped to Eloquent models (`app/Models/`) and then used appropriately inside the code to fetch needed data.
- Redis is used as a caching solution for performance optimization.

5. User Interface (UI):

- Uses Blade templates (`resources/views/`) as the base user interface rendering technology to render dashboards and data tables.
- Mapbox GL JS and Google Maps JavaScript APIs are used to display infrastructure, waterways and thematic map layers on interactive maps.
- Additional self-developed JavaScript libraries containing mainly utility functions exist in `resources/js/`.

3.3. Observatory data analysis procedures

The Corridor Observatory is designed not only as a data repository but as a decision-support tool, transforming raw information into actionable insights. Calculating analytics, KPIs, and performance metrics is essential for achieving the objectives outlined in Task 3.4, which focuses on enhancing corridor visibility and supporting regional decision-making and policy development.

By aggregating and analysing operational and infrastructure data, the Observatory provides users with a clear picture of corridor performance. Metrics such as traffic volumes, lock availability, congestion levels, environmental impact indicators and alerts-related analytics allow for evidence-based decisions for improving reliability, efficiency and sustainability. These insights also support strategic planning, allowing authorities to identify bottlenecks, prioritize investments and monitor resilience over time.

The analytical procedures implemented in the Observatory follow a structured approach (Figure 14):

- **Data Collection, Preprocessing & Storage** by gathering static and dynamic datasets from multiple sources, validating formats and ensuring interoperability. Next step is storing them in a relational database for persistence.
- **Metrics Calculation** by applying algorithms and executing database queries to compute various KPIs.
- **Visualization & Interpretation** by presenting results through dashboards, charts, and geospatial maps for intuitive understanding.
- **Continuous Feedback Loop** by integrating pilot roll-out results to refine analytics and improve accuracy.

Ultimately, these procedures establish that the Corridor Observatory evolves from a static data platform into a dynamic, insight-driven system, providing users with useful information.

Figure 14 Corridor Observatory Analytics extraction process

The Data Collection process involves retrieving information from multiple data sources, including AIPo, EuRIS, Polish Government datasets and the Digital Twin. While the full procedure is detailed in Deliverable D3.5, this section provides an overview of how these datasets are prepared for analysis within the Corridor Observatory.

Once data is fetched, minimal preprocessing is applied to verify they are compatible with the application's database schema. Dedicated tables store either raw data for metric computation or pre-calculated insights and KPIs. For performance reasons, metrics are computed through scheduled jobs at defined intervals, reducing system load and avoiding database bottlenecks. Some calculations are computationally intensive, requiring smart caching strategies using Redis to optimize response times. Caching is applied primarily to derived metrics at the river level, making dashboards and visualizations quickly accessible.

The backend relies heavily on Laravel's Eloquent ORM for database interactions; however, certain analytics demand complex Structured Query Language (SQL) queries to efficiently handle large datasets and intricate joins. In these cases, raw SQL is employed to achieve optimal performance without compromising accuracy.

The following table details the database tables used for metric computation, their data types, the corresponding Eloquent models and the metrics derived from each.

Table 2 Table presenting database tables used for metrics calculation

DB Table	Description	Table type	Eloquent model	Metrics calculated
river_stats	General river metrics	Metrics	RiverStat	Length, Basin Area, Average Discharge, Traffic Volume, Availability, Reliability, Safety, Environmental Impact, Cost Efficiency, CO ₂ Emission Savings
ivers	The rivers' data and geoinformation	Data	River	Helper table for fetching relationships with other tables for metrics calculation
river_sections	The rivers' segmentation	Data	RiverSection	Helper table for fetching relationships with other tables for metrics calculation
locks	The rivers' locks	Data	Lock	Number of locks
bridges	The rivers' bridges	Data	Bridge	Number of bridges
locks_availability	Lock availabilities periods	Data	LockAvailability	Lock Availability, Availability Loss Percentage, Least/Most Available Locks
alerts	Alerts and notices to skippers	Data	Alerts	Number of alerts, Alert density, Alerts Count, Average Alert Duration
alert_types	Alert categories	Data	AlertType	Number of alerts, Alerts Count, Average Alert Duration (Days)

The Infrastructure Index tab provides a high-level overview of general river-related metrics. Users can select a specific river, Po, Seine, Moselle, Vistula, or Oder via a dedicated button group. Within the River Infrastructure & Characteristics section, key indicators and metrics are displayed to establish the infrastructure baseline for corridor evaluation.

- **Name:** The name of the river imported manually.
- **Source and Mouth locations:** The start and end of the river, imported manually.
- **Length (km):** The length of the navigable part of the river, imported manually.
- **Basin area (km²):** The land area that drains into a single river, imported manually.
- **Average discharge (m³/s):** The water volume flowing into a river for a period of time, imported manually.
- **Locks:** The total number of locks found on the river, imported manually from sectional data.
- **Bridges:** The total number of bridges found on the river, imported manually from sectional data.

To ensure optimal performance, database queries are minimized and fully optimized. Most metrics are calculated using a single Eloquent query that retrieves all necessary data in one operation. This approach leverages eager loading, a technique that fetches related data alongside the primary model to prevent the N+1 query problem commonly associated with lazy loading [1]. By doing so, the system reduces query overhead and improves responsiveness. The query not only retrieves river metrics but also fetches geospatial data required for rendering the corridor infrastructure on the interactive map.

```
$riverData = River::with([
    'riverStats' => function ($query) {
        $query->orderBy('id', 'DESC');
    },
    'sections' => function ($query) {
        $query->withCount('locks');
        $query->withCount('bridges');
    },
    'sections.locks.lockAvailabilities' => function ($query) use ($from_date, $to_date) {
        $query->whereDate('from_date', '>=', $from_date);
        $query->whereDate('to_date', '<=', $to_date);
        $query->orderBy('updated_at', 'DESC');
    },
    'sensors'
])
->where('id', $river_id)
->orderBy('id', 'ASC')
->first();
```

The Operational Metrics tab focuses on river operations, presenting aggregated analytics such as:

- **Last Report:** The name of the last general river statistics imported manually.
- **Traffic volume (tons/year):** The yearly cargo volume moved by vessel traffic, imported manually.

- **Availability (%)**: The time the infrastructure is usable, imported manually.
- **Reliability (%)**: How consistent is the waterway in terms, influenced by infrastructure availability, wait and travel times, imported manually.
- **Safety (accidents/(1000 km))**: A measure of accidents per 1000km, imported manually.
- **Environmental Impact (kg CO₂/(ton · km))**: How much carbon is emitted for moving one ton of cargo for one kilometer, imported manually.
- **Cost Efficiency (€/(ton · km))**: A theoretical amount of cost to move cargo, imported manually.
- **CO₂ Emission Savings (kg year)**: The difference between the emissions generated by moving the cargo by truck minus the emissions actually generated by moving them by barge, imported manually.

The same optimized query used for the Infrastructure Index also powers the Operational Metrics Over Time chart, which supports filtering by predefined intervals of 6 months, 1 year, or 2 years to visualize performance trends.

```
$chartData = RiverStat::where('river_id', $river_id)
    ->where(function ($query) use ($startDate, $endDate) {
        $query->where(function ($query) use ($startDate, $endDate) {
            $query->where('from_date', '>=', $startDate)
                ->where('from_date', '<=', $endDate);
        });
    })
    ->orderBy('id', 'ASC')->get();
```

Future versions of the SCMS will introduce a more dynamic way of calculating the above metrics based on real-world route planning scenarios, integrating data from the Disruption Impact Estimation module to provide even more context-aware insights.

The secondary Alerts Metrics panel gives users the possibility to query for alerts metrics according to a specified timeframe. The metrics displayed are:

- **Total Alerts**: The total alerts count for the specified time period.
- **Total Alerts per Alert Type**: A table that displays the data grouped by Alert Type:
 - **Alert type**: The alert category.
 - **Alerts Count**: The total alerts count for the given category.
 - **Average Duration (Days)**: The average duration of the alerts for the given timeframe.
- **Alert Density**: An alert density heatmap is displayed inside the Corridor Observatory web-based map that ranges from Low to High. It is calculated by utilizing the geodata of each alert.

For Alerts Metrics, a more advanced query is required to handle complex aggregations. In this case, Laravel's Query Builder is used instead of Eloquent as it offers an excellent programming interface and greater flexibility for sophisticated SQL operations [2].

```
$overlapCondition = function (EloquentBuilder | QueryBuilder $query) use ($alertsFromDate,
$alertsToDate) {
```

```

$query->where('valid_from', '<=', $alertsToDate)
->where(function (EloquentBuilder|QueryBuilder $nestedQuery) use ($alertsFromDate) {
    $nestedQuery->whereNull('valid_to')
    ->orWhere('valid_to', '>=', $alertsFromDate);
});
};

$alerts_count = Alert::where('river_id', $river_id)
->where($overlapCondition)
->count();

$alerts_metrics_by_type = DB::table('alerts AS a')
->join('alert_types AS t', 'a.alert_type_id', '=', 't.id')
->selectRaw(
    "LOWER(t.description) as description,
    COUNT(a.id) AS count,
    AVG(
        TIMESTAMPDIFF(
            DAY,
            COALESCE(
                CASE
                    WHEN a.valid_from IN ('0001-01-01 00:00:00', '1000-01-01 00:00:00')
                    THEN NULL
                    ELSE a.valid_from
                END,
                ?
            ),
            COALESCE(
                CASE
                    WHEN a.valid_to IN ('9999-12-31 23:59:59', '9999-12-31 00:00:00')
                    THEN NULL
                    ELSE a.valid_to
                END,
                ?
            )
        ) AS average_duration_days,
    JSON_ARRAYAGG(
        JSON_OBJECT(
            'id', a.id,
            'from_point_lat', a.from_point_lat,
            'from_point_long', a.from_point_long
        )
    )

```

```
    ) AS alerts_data",
    [$alertsFromDate, $alertsToDate]
  )
  ->where('a.river_id', $river_id)
  ->where($overlapCondition)
  ->whereNotNull('a.from_point_lat')
  ->whereNotNull('a.from_point_long')
  ->whereNotNull('a.to_point_lat')
  ->whereNotNull('a.to_point_long')
  ->groupBy('description')
  ->orderByDesc('count')
  ->get()
  ->mapWithKeys(function ($row) {
    $title = Str::title($row->description);

    $alerts = json_decode($row->alerts_data, true);

    $features = array_map(function ($alert) use ($title) {
      return [
        'type' => 'Feature',
        'properties' => [
          'alert_type' => $title,
          'alert_id' => $alert['id'],
        ],
        'geometry' => [
          'type' => 'Point',
          'coordinates' => [
            (float) $alert['from_point_long'],
            (float) $alert['from_point_lat']
          ]
        ]
      ];
    }, $alerts);

    return [
      $title => [
        'count' => (int) $row->count,
        'average_duration_days' => number_format($row->average_duration_days, 0, ',', '.'),
        'alerts_heatmap_geojson_features' => $features,
      ]
    ];
  })
  ->toArray();
```

This query calculates the total alerts within a specified timeframe, breaks them down by alert type, computes the average duration (in days), and returns a GeoJSON array containing the geographic coordinates, latitude and longitude, of each alert for map visualization.

The Infrastructure Metrics tab provides the most granular insights, focusing on lock availability over time. Users can filter by river, timeframe, or lock name to access detailed performance data.

- **General locks overview:** The search results containing the matched locks according to the search criteria. Although not a metric itself, the results offered contain the necessary user interface elements to inspect the useful metrics.
- **Least Available Locks:** The search results returned above, are filtered further to find the least available locks in the specified timeframe.
- **Most Available Locks:** The search results returned above, are filtered further to find the most available locks in the specified timeframe.

The least and most available locks are calculated by filtering the existing locks fetched in the initial query mentioned for the Infrastructure Index. Having the necessary lock data, the next step is to perform efficient filtering by utilizing Laravel collections inside a PHP class method. Laravel Collections provide a convenient programming interface for working with arrays of data, providing a plethora of utility methods for easy and effective array manipulation [3].

```
protected const EPSILON = 1e-6;

public static function calculateLeastAndMostAvailableLocks(array $locks): array {
    $locksCollection = collect($locks);

    if ($locksCollection->isEmpty()) {
        $mostAvailableCollection = collect();
        $leastAvailableCollection = collect();
        $maxAvailability = null;
        $minAvailability = null;
    } else {
        $maxAvailability = $locksCollection->max('availability');
        $minAvailability = $locksCollection->min('availability');

        $mostAvailableCollection = $locksCollection->filter(
            fn($lock) => isset($lock['availability']) && abs($lock['availability'] - $maxAvailability) <
self::EPSILON
        );

        $leastAvailableCollection = $locksCollection->filter(
            fn($lock) => isset($lock['availability']) && abs($lock['availability'] - $minAvailability) <
self::EPSILON
        );
    }
}
```

```
return [$leastAvailableCollection, $mostAvailableCollection];  
}
```

The filtering anonymous functions use a tolerance to safely compare floating-point numbers that represent lock availability. Instead of checking for exact equality which can fail due to small rounding errors in floating-point arithmetic, they check whether the difference between two values is smaller than a predefined threshold (`EPSILON`). If the absolute difference is less than this very small number, the values are considered effectively equal. This approach makes sure that locks with availability values that are practically the same are grouped together as “most available” or “least available,” even if minor computational imprecision exists.

4. User roles and accessibility

This chapter explains the different user roles within the Corridor Visibility and Open Data Platform and provides an overview of the observatory's accessibility features for using its core components, i.e. the infrastructure index, operational metrics, and infrastructure metrics, guiding users in how these can be navigated and applied. A short, but detailed video tutorial covering the main functionalities of the observatory is available on the SCMS platform to support effective use of its tools and services for both operational and strategic purposes

4.1. User personas

The Corridor Observatory platform caters to a broad spectrum of users involved in multimodal logistics, inland waterway transport (IWT), infrastructure oversight, and regional planning. To ensure the platform meets the practical and strategic needs of its user base, the following representative user profiles have been defined. These profiles reflect the technical roles within the system and also the real-world actors contributing to the CRISTAL project's corridor visibility objectives.

1. System Administrators

- *Platform Role:* System Admin
- *Typical Users:* IT leads from the responsible consortium partner, CERTH

2. Company Administrators

- *Platform Role:* Company Admin
- *Typical Users:* Logistics managers, fleet coordinators, operations directors from shipping companies, barge operators

3. Stakeholders

- *Platform Role:* Stakeholder
- *Typical Users:* Public authorities, infrastructure managers, environmental agencies, research institutions, pilot site coordinators, project partners

The platform roles are almost the same that are used for the SCMS platform, as the Corridor Observatory will be a part of the SCMS application. By identifying these user profiles, the platform's interface, features, and training materials can be better aligned with the specific expectations and workflows of each group. This user-centric approach supports the broader aims of Task 3.4 for enhancing corridor transparency, enabling data-informed planning, and fostering collaboration across the transport ecosystem.

4.2. Use cases

The following table outlines the user personas, their platform roles and their primary use cases for the Corridor Observatory platform.

Table 3 User personas and use case mapping

User Persona	Platform Role	Primary Use Cases
System Administrator	System Admin	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Configure and maintain data pipelines for corridor visibility - Ensure data integrity and system uptime - Manage access controls and integration settings
Company Administrator	Company Admin	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Access infrastructure and operational data - Monitor corridor-level KPIs and metrics
Stakeholder	Stakeholder	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Access strategic data insights - Monitor infrastructure conditions - Support policy-making and planning - Evaluate long-term corridor performance and resilience

The user personas and their corresponding use cases for the Corridor Observatory platform, as outlined above, are instrumental in ensuring that the system delivers targeted value across operational, analytical, and strategic domains. By clearly defining these roles and interactions, the platform is positioned to support various stakeholders, from technical administrators to policy-makers. This structured approach guarantees that the observatory's services are functional and accessible.

4.3. Accessibility remarks

The deliverable D3.3 highlights accessibility as a fundamental consideration in the design of the Synchronic Modal Corridor Management System (SCMS). The platform aims to offer inclusive, consistent, and future-proof user experience by following international standards including the Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG 2.1 AA), the European Accessibility Act (2019/882), and relevant national regulations.

The foundation for ensuring that all SCMS modules, including the Corridor Observatory and Common Open Data Platform which was developed to be seamlessly integrated to the SCMS, can be utilized successfully by a variety of stakeholders, is established by the standards outlined in D3.3 being perceivable, operable, understandable, and robust (POUR).

Expanding upon this structure, the "Corridor Observatory" page integrates accessibility into its layout and operation. Although the Corridor Observatory is mainly a data-driven and visualization-focused module, its user interface has been carefully designed to guarantee inclusivity, clarity, and usability:

- **Infrastructure Index:** Scrollable, high-contrast data panels with readable type and multiple visual signals (such as borders and spacing, in addition to colors) are how the river infrastructure data are displayed. Important metrics like river length, discharge, and locks count are therefore ensured to be available on all devices and be read with the help of assistive technology (Figure 15 and Figure 16).

The screenshot displays a web interface for the 'Infrastructure Index'. At the top, there is a 'Select River' section with a list of rivers: PO (selected), SEINE, MOSELLE, VISTULA, and ODER. Below this, there are three tabs: 'Infrastructure Index' (active), 'Operational Metrics', and 'Infrastructure Metrics'. The main content area is titled 'River Infrastructure & Characteristics' and contains a table of data for the Po river.

River Infrastructure & Characteristics					
Name	Po	Source Name	Monte Viso	Mouth Name	Adriatic Sea
Length	652 km	Basin Area	74000 km ²	Average Discharge	1540 m ³ /sec
Locks	17	Bridges	100		

Figure 15 Accessibility elements in Infrastructure Index, desktop view

scms.imet.gr

Figure 16 Accessibility elements in Infrastructure Index, mobile view

- **Operational Metrics:** To guarantee that users can explore and filter statistics and KPIs without any problem, the dashboard has interactive charts and input tools (drop-down menus, radio buttons) with clear descriptions. All selection fields enable keyboard accessibility, and users who utilize non-mouse input methods are guided by visual focus indicators (Figure 17 and Figure 18).

Figure 17 Accessibility elements in Operational Metrics, desktop view

Figure 18 Accessibility elements in Operational Metrics, desktop view

- **Infrastructure Metrics:** Consistent labels, accessible date pickers, and informative placeholders are used in forms to select timeframes and lock names. These characteristics help reduce cognitive load and improve usability for individuals with memory or visual processing issues (Figure 19 and Figure 20).

Figure 19 Accessibility elements in Infrastructure Metrics, desktop view

Figure 20 Accessibility elements in Infrastructure Metrics, mobile view

Therefore, the Corridor Observatory integrates accessibility into both its visual and interface design (contrast, redundant cues, predictable organization) as well as its technological design (semantic HTML, Accessible Rich Internet Applications (ARIA) roles, responsive layouts). This ensures that the Corridor Observatory is an inclusive platform that is in line with the international and European accessibility standards in addition to being an effective analytical instrument.

5. Challenges & risk mitigation

5.1. Data gathering & digitalization

One of the biggest challenges encountered during the development of the Corridor Observatory was the availability and digitalization of data across all pilot sites. While the platform relies on structured, interoperable datasets to deliver accurate insights, sourcing such data proved difficult. In many cases, live operational data was scarce and pilots had to rely on mock or test datasets to validate functionality. Although these datasets were useful for demonstrating core features, they lacked the variability and reliability required for real-time performance monitoring.

Digitizing legacy data sources presented another major hurdle. Much of the information provided by regional authorities or older monitoring systems was not designed for digital interoperability, requiring extensive manual extraction, formatting and validation before integration. Converting these datasets into machine-readable formats such as JSON was often time-consuming and, in some cases, partially achievable. Where full digitization was not possible, semi-dynamic update methods were implemented to ensure at least partial availability of critical data like Notices to Skippers.

Despite these limitations, progress was made in securing the data required to make the Corridor Observatory operational and able to provide meaningful insights to the users. The efforts laid the groundwork for alert generation and corridor visibility, but they also highlighted the need for standardized, scalable and interoperable data infrastructures.

5.2. Software development

Developing the software Corridor Observatory presented several technical challenges, primarily due to data limitations and complex processing requirements. One of the most significant risks was building features without access to complete or reliable datasets. In many cases, data was either unavailable or only partially digitized, making it difficult to validate functionality and increasing the likelihood of developing software components that could not be fully utilized.

On the backend, implementing advanced analytics required computationally intensive operations, such as calculating aggregated metrics and performance indicators across large datasets. These operations often involved complex SQL queries, which needed careful optimization to avoid excessive database load. To maintain responsiveness, smart caching strategies were introduced for computationally heavy database queries, ensuring that frequently accessed results could be served efficiently without compromising system performance.

Another major challenge was handling geospatial data for the Corridor Observatory's interactive map. Large volumes of geodata had to be processed and returned in formats such as GeoJSON, requiring efficient backend workflows to minimize latency. On the frontend, rendering these datasets in a performant way demanded optimized JavaScript techniques to manage dynamic layers, heatmaps and interactive elements without degrading user experience. Achieving this level of performance was essential to deliver a custom Web-GIS-like interface capable of supporting real-time visualization and user interaction.

6. Conclusions

The Corridor Observatory plays a critical role within both the SCMS platform and the CRISTAL project, offering value on multiple levels. Firstly, it leverages the extensive data collected through its functionalities, i.e. the early detection and alert system, the disruption impact estimation and the action toolbox of services (track and trace, smart bulletin, estimated time of arrival (ETA) calculation), to provide metrics and analytics related to river operations from an infrastructural perspective. These insights, including the status of locks and other key infrastructure, are particularly valuable for local-level policy making, enabling targeted investments to strengthen river transport systems. By identifying bottlenecks and weak points in the river transport network, the observatory supports more efficient allocation of resources and the strategic promotion of rivers as a mode of transportation, especially for cargo.

Secondly, the analytics derived from the observatory's data are instrumental for operational decision-making over the medium to long term. Transport operators and stakeholders gain a comprehensive overview of river operational status and reliability, which can inform decisions to maintain or expand river transport activities. For stakeholders not currently using inland waterways, the insights provided by the observatory can serve as an incentive to invest in river transport, directly supporting one of the project's key objectives: achieving a 20% increase in the modal share of inland navigation.

The development of the Corridor Observatory, while straightforward from a programming and algorithmic perspective, faced challenges due to limited digitalization and data availability, a common issue in less developed river systems. Moreover, calculating meaningful metrics required substantial data collection from the rivers, constrained by the project's timeframe. Despite these challenges, the observatory was successfully developed and tested using appropriate methods, including the use of historical and test data. In addition, the Corridor Observatory was designed with scalability and extensibility in mind: additional metrics, data sources and data analysis procedures can be incorporated in the future, beyond the project's duration, ensuring that the system's analytical value continues to grow and evolve.

Overall, the Corridor Observatory represents a significant advancement for both operational and strategic management of river transport, providing a robust, open and publicly accessible platform that supports informed decision-making, policy development, and future enhancements in inland navigation.

7. References

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